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Editorial

Disseminate Research in Science, Technology, Engineering and Mathematics (STEM) that Help in Creating Constructive Solutions in a Context of National and International Regulations

Welcome to the open access, multi disciplines Journal of Civil Engineering and Environmental Sciences (JCEES).

We are delighted to announce that all the original work in the engineering, sciences and environment can be covered under the scope of JCEES. In the Civil Engineering and Environmental Science, we are bringing together the new ideas of different research activities from different fields (chemical, biological, and engineering related to environment and health) to encourage and advance the multidisciplinary research. It has been well known that there is a strong relations/interactions between the environmental compartments (air, water, and soil), and that understanding the chemical reactions and the biological interactions in all the environmental compartments provides insight in making decision on how to protect environment and human health. Therefore, we are putting together the real knowledge into the hands of everyone who are interested in understanding the chemical and the biological transformation of pollutants; this information together can be used to develop targeted solutions to pollution.

It is our aim to disseminate research in Science, Technology, Engineering and Mathematics (STEM) that help in creating constructive solutions in a context of national and international regulations.

Although the Journal of Civil Engineering and Environmental Sciences primarily devoted to expand our understanding in the sciences related environmental pollutants, environmental toxicology, chemistry, biology, mathematics and engineering, it is also devoted to peer-reviewed articles about other new discoveries.

The Journal of Civil Engineering and Environmental Sciences provides findings including chemical, physical and biological process affecting flora, fauna, water, air and soil, also presents papers describing methods used in study of environmental pollutants,

environmental toxicology, engineering and mathematics.

Papers submitted to the JCEES must meet certain criteria; must be subject to peer review; and must be professional articles buttressed with experimental and/or analytical information. The author's writing should show competency in the subject discussed. And the author's knowledge of the literature should be apparent and sources cited. Articles of local and international interests are welcome to be submitted to the Journal of Civil Engineering and Environmental Sciences. Articles that replicate knowledge or techniques will be rejected without review. Submitted articles must have up-to-date references, and employ the experimental replication and statistical analysis.

Papers published by editor's choice are meant to challenge the reader with new ideas, new experimental results and new anomalies that challenge existing hypotheses or theories. The editor accepts all responsibility for any mistakes that made by publishing articles that are not substantiated by experimental facts. Critical examinations of all papers are encouraged and professional letters to the editor will be published and shared with the authors. Readers may express a difference of opinion "unsupported by factual evidences"; however, experimental evidence is preferred.

The Journal of Civil Engineering and Environmental Sciences especially welcomes experimental data, even if preliminary; and inadequate theories should be challenged by experimental facts.

We aim to accelerate progress in the STEM; therefore, the Journal of Civil Engineering and Environmental Sciences designed to be an open access journal to research. And we encourage people to permit the content to be used without restriction which will change the way people think, learn and communicate; and will help scientists sharing findings to encourage faster progress in solving scientific problems.

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